

A smart-sensing AI-driven platform for scalable, low-cost hydroponic units

D3.2 GOhydro AI Models v2.0

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ACRONYMS LIST

CHSK	Crop Health Sensor Kit
CSU	Communication and Storage Unit
MMS	Multi-modal Sensor Kit
NCK	Nutrient-content Kit
PLS	Partial Least Squares
LMS	Least Mean Squares
SVR	Support Vector Regression
CNN	Convolutional Neural Networks
CLNN	Cascade Learning Neural Networks

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present report provides an overview of the operational framework and design of the GOhydro AI models, i.e., the components responsible for performing predictive analysis over the data collected via the Sensor Kit embedded in the GOhydro hydroponic platform.

The report describes in brief the baseline knowledge to which the models rely, the data over which it operates, and the algorithmic families that will be tested as real data are being collected during the GOhydro trials. Finally, the report clarifies the architectural placement of the AI components in the context of the data platform that serves the overall GOhydro solution.

1 INTRODUCTION

GOhydro aims to develop a cost-efficient smart-sensing ICT platform capable of monitoring the crops' health and nutrient content of hydroponically cultivated microgreens in order to optimize the cultivation process and allow the harvest of the best possible products in any hydroponic installation. In the bigger picture, the project aspires to culminate in the production of a radical platform that will be a shifting paradigm of how AI-driven technological innovation can become an affordable, accessible-by-all and user-friendly tool applicable to all forms of urban farming.

Towards this objective, the provision of robust, accurate predictive models that will determine the state of the cultivation based on sensing data and provide actionable guidance to the users is one of the core aspirations of the project and the GOhydro product itself. In this context, WP3 aims to put in place the AI framework that will make the most of the available data and the deep insights built in the context of WP1 and constitute an effective and performant recommendation and decision support sub-system.

D3.2 deals with the design and development of such models that will fulfil the aforementioned analytical requirements. It aims, on one hand, to properly interpret and contextualise the available sensing data and their correlation to optimal cultivation settings as produced by WP2 and WP1 respectively. And on the other hand, implement them under the data platform architecture specified in D3.1 ensuring the efficient exposure of the analytical results to the GOhydro application and external/future applications.

The present report summarises the methodological approach for developing the GOhydro predictive models, the data representation and technical choices for designing and implementing the models, as well as the establishment of their training and validation framework within the GOhydro data platform.

2 SCOPE OF AI PREDICTIVE COMPONENTS

2.1 OVERALL CONCEPT AND PURPOSE

In the context of GOhydro, AI components serve as the enabler of the monitoring and recommendation functions of the overall solution. The aim is for the data platform underlying the end-user application to continuously get informed of the state of a cultivation in a given installation, provide visual analytics to the user/manager of the platform, and forward tending tips to optimise the cultivation process.

Cultivation Optimisation is assessed against the optimal recipes as determined by WP1 studies, regarding the different microgreen species covered. Furthermore, they are modelled as correlative to the environmental conditions, as well as certain light and water parameters within the hydroponic unit. It is, moreover, measured by the physical and chemical parameters presented in deliverable D1.2.

The purpose of the models, is thus, to solve a *regression* problem associating the obtained measurements with the expected physical and chemical measurements of the resulting yield.

2.2 DATA REPRESENTATION

The GOhydro predictive models are trained over the data accumulated via the various pilot trials conducted in the context of WP4 of the project, and following the protocols specified in the context of WP4. As such, training data followed the structure specified in deliverable D4.1, trial protocols for microgreens production in hydroponic units, and covered the following parameters.

Parameter	Unit of measurement
Stem length	mm
Internode length	mm
Number of leaves	no
Number of plants	no/cm ²
Leaves area	cm ²
Fresh Weight	g tray (992 cm ²)
Dry Weight	g tray (992 cm ²)
Total phenols	mg/kg

These are measured post-facto after the yield has been collected and uploaded to the data platform, in order to be incorporated in the training set along with the data collected by the GOhydro Multi-model Sensor Kit (MMS). The latter, and in particular its Crop Health Sensor Kit (CHSK) component, are cached into the platform’s communication unit (CSU) and periodically sent via the relevant API calls to the underlying Quantum instance. The data are annotated with identification information of the installation, and measurements are timestamped. JSON is used as the data exchange format between the communicating entities. An exemplary JSON structure from a GOhydro pilot installation data is presented in the following figure. For each data point, the exact timestamp of each measurement provided by the sensors incorporated in the CHSK is included along with the measured value, i.e. four different timeseries are taken into account for each cultivation setting.

```
[
  {
    "_id": {
      "$oid": "62d423402c34c9459e30fdc9"
    },
    "controller_id": "E4:5F:01:47:4C:71",
    "data_kits": [
      {
        "sensor_kit_id": "B8:27:EB:2C:B8:9D",
        "data_points": [
          {
            "sensor": "PH_Meter",
            "value": "7.17",
            "timestamp": "2022-07-17T16:46:32"
          },
          {
            "sensor": "TDS_Meter",
            "value": "9.83",
            "timestamp": "2022-07-17T16:46:32"
          },
          {
            "sensor": "Air_Humidity",
            "value": "31.43",
            "timestamp": "2022-07-17T16:46:32"
          },
          {
            "sensor": "UV_light",
            "value": "0.02",
            "timestamp": "2022-07-17T16:46:32"
          }
        ]
      }
    ]
  }
]
```

Figure 1: Sample of JSON data structure communicated from the CSU to the Data Platform

3 DESIGN & EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

To efficiently tackle the different predictive cases for each target variable, a process for automatically building neural architectures for the different problems was set up, producing different networks for the different predictive problems.

The neural networks implementing the prediction models were discovered through an automated architecture generation and validation process, aiming to specify the simplest (shallowest) architecture that achieves the optimal precision/generalization capacity/explainability balance. The generator produces multi-layered feed-forward neural networks organised in a cascaded topology (Fahlman, 1990). Each neuron in the network uses a hyperbolic tangent as its activation function, because of its antisymmetric properties. The exception is the output layer, where the node(s) use a linear activation function.

The training of the models was performed in batch mode, i.e., all training data were fed to the network under training simultaneously. Training followed the iRprop methodology ((Riedmiller, 1993), (Igel, 2003)), which uses only the sign of the error function gradient to propagate the gradient. Thus, it is more robust with respect to its ability to manage very large or very small gradient values, avoiding possible overflow and precision issues respectively.

The training process for all models entailed the configuration of the network builder with different parameters values for the targeted MSE and the split of the available dataset into training and testing subsets, in order to determine the architecture with sufficient performance and generalisation capacity.

3.1 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP WITHIN THE GOHYDRO DATA PLATFORM

As detailed in deliverable D3.1, the produced AI models are integrated into the overall GOhydro data infrastructure and constitute the *AI Pipeline* layer of the platform (lower left of Figure 1). In essence, the AI Pipeline entails the training and operationalisation of the models, using data as they are collected in the persistence layer.

The training part is profile-independent, i.e., all collected data are used for re-training and re-calibrating the components, taking into account the particularities of a setup as additional features (e.g., geographical location of the installation). In contrast, the execution workflow uses the latest version of the models as derived from their latest training session, to analyse and produce recommendations for a given installation/user.

All AI components are implemented in Python and containerised in Docker instances for their deployment under the Quantum platform. Their communication with the persistence layer is realised via the API calls exposed by the latter's databases, to collect both measurement and installation-specific data and build the overall training datasets and inputs for the models.

Figure 2: GOhydro data platform - high-level architecture

4 MODELS CHARACTERISTICS AND PERFORMANCE

Following the discussed methodology, neural network architectures were produced for each examined species and for selected target parameters, namely fresh weight, dry weight, and phenols). The characteristics and performance for each model are presented in the following subsections.

4.1 MODELS FOR BASIL

4.1.1 Fresh weight predictor

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	6
Total Nodes	11
Total Connections	368
LMS Capacity	37

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.353
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.276
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.525
R-squared (R ²)	0.912

4.1.2 Dry weight predictor

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	86
Total Nodes	114
Total Connections	6454
LMS Capacity	103

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.382
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.260
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.510
R-squared (R ²)	0.823

4.1.3 Phenols predictor

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	61
Total Nodes	135
Total Connections	7522
LMS Capacity	92

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.271
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.166
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.407
R-squared (R ²)	0.810

4.2 MODELS FOR BRUSSELS SPROUT

4.2.1 Fresh weight predictor

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	8
Total Nodes	13
Total Connections	426
LMS Capacity	42

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.389
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.294
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.542
R-squared (R ²)	0.919

4.2.2 Dry weight predictor

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	47
Total Nodes	206
Total Connections	16088
LMS Capacity	66

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.358
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.294
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.542
R-squared (R ²)	0.874

4.2.3 Phenols predictor

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	124
Total Nodes	349

Total Connections	22272
LMS Capacity	155

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.229
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.224
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.473
R-squared (R ²)	0.801

4.3 MODELS FOR LETTUCE

4.3.1 Fresh weight predictor

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	6
Total Nodes	15
Total Connections	493
LMS Capacity	37

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.310
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.160
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.399
R-squared (R ²)	0.919

4.3.2 Dry weight predictor

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	50
Total Nodes	219
Total Connections	18197
LMS Capacity	71

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.328
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.281
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.539
R-squared (R ²)	0.843

4.3.3 Phenols predictor

Parameter	Value
Number of Hidden Layers	56
Total Nodes	114
Total Connections	6847
LMS Capacity	91

Metric	Value
Mean Absolute Error (MAE)	0.285
Mean Square Error (MSE)	0.286
Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)	0.534
R-squared (R ²)	0.798

5 CONCLUSIONS

The report serves as a companion to the GOhydro AI models implementation, providing a high-level overview of the design and development considerations of the relevant components.

It describes the methodology adopted for producing the predictors for each target variable, and the way the models are integrated in the GOhydro platform.

As presented in Section 4, some target variables required substantially more complex networks for obtaining a reliable predictor. The fact implies that further improvement pathways are possible, via possibly integrating additional monitoring devices or periodically feeding the system with laboratory measurements of product samples in addition to live data. These point to promising directions for the extension of the GOhydro platform in the future and the establishment of products with broader coverage.